

Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from the ship 'Bispevika 7', Oslo.

Aoife Daly, Ph.d.
Dendro.dk report 37 : 2016
Commissioned by Hilde Vangstad, Sarah Fawsitt & Andreas Kerr, Norsk Maritimt Museum.

Two samples from a ship found during excavations in Oslo were submitted for dendrochronological analysis. This is one of 16 ships found at the site of Bispevika, and has been named 'Bispevika 7'. Both samples are from planks from the ship and are both made of *Quercus sp.*, oak.

Fig. 1. Bispevika 7, Oslo. Diagram showing the chronological position of the tree-ring curves from the timbers from the boat.

Plank x108

Plank x108 is radially converted from the parent tree, contains 147 tree-rings of which 7 are sapwood rings. The sample is dated. The tree-ring curve from this plank covers the period AD 1401-1547. Allowing for missing sapwood, the felling date for the tree that was used to make plank x108 is estimated to be c. AD 1548-61.

Plank x133

Plank x133 is tangentially converted from the parent tree, contains 133 tree-rings, all heartwood. The tree-ring curve covers the period AD 1354-1486. Again allowing for missing sapwood, the estimated felling date for the tree that was used to make plank x131 is placed at after c. AD 1494 (fig. 1).

If it is assumed that the timbers for the building of the ship took place on one occasion, then it is the dating of plank x108 that provides this dating, at AD 1548-61 (marked with green in fig. 1).

The tree-ring curves from the two samples from Bispevika 7 achieve correlation between each other with a *t*-value of $t = 3,94$. An average of these two has been calculated (Z173M001) which covers the period AD 1354-1547. The correlation between this average curve and a range of site and master chronologies for Northern Europe is shown in table 1. The highest correlations are achieved with datasets from west Sweden and with ships and other objects that are shown through dendrochronology to be of west Swedish oak.

FileNames	-	-	Z173M001	
-	start	dates	AD1354	
-	dates	end	AD1547	
Z119M001	AD1317	AD1573	10,07	Barcode ship 04 BC04 Oslo 5 timbers (Daly 2015a)
SM000012	AD1125	AD1720	9,66	Sverige Vest (Bråthen 1982)
q415029m04	AD1356	AD1540	8,94	Evangelistas altarpiece Seville Cathedral Swedish timber imports 29 planks (Rodríguez-Trobajo & Domínguez-Delmás 2015)
Z040M001	AD1386	AD1567	8,13	Gåsehage Boat Randers 2 timbers (Daly 2009a)
Z043M001	AD1320	AD1577	7,36	FPL 77 4AM wreck 5 timbers (Daly 2009b)
CD60HZ01	AD1341	AD1551	6,70	Denmark Sostrup 6 timbers (Nationalmuseet revised Daly 2007)
00652M02	AD1405	AD1607	6,52	Copenhagen B&W Grund Vrag 2. 2 trees (Daly 1997)
00651m03	AD1303	AD1585	6,52	Copenhagen B&W Grund Vrag 1 3 trees (Daly 1997)
B027Mpurple2	AD1275	AD1532	6,33	Copenhagen Gl Strand IMPORTS 12 timbers (Daly forthcoming)
B0275Morange2	AD1331	AD1557	6,28	Copenhagen Gl Strand IMPORTS 24 timbers (Daly forthcoming)
midtjy17	AD536	AD1980	6,26	Mid Jutland (Christensen pers comm)
ZEALAND0	AD452	AD1770	6,14	Sjælland Denmark 249 timbers (Daly unpubl)
SM100001	AD1310	AD1539	6,12	Sweden Ystad area (Lund University)
2121M002	AD1052	AD1596	6,04	Suså Næstved all posts (Daly 2001)
Z141M001	AD1352	AD1539	5,74	Klippan 2 shipwreck Västergötland 11 timbers (Daly 2015b)
B028M003	AD1386	AD1576	5,68	Køge Havn 4 timbers (Daly 2013)
EP41592	AD1390	AD1592	5,64	Stirling Castle Episode 4 Swedish imports (Crone pers comm)
Z027M002	AD1313	AD1567	5,58	Amager Strand ship 9 timbers (Daly 2008)
6094M002	AD1450	AD1660	5,57	Funder kirke later material 4 timbers (Daly 2002)

Table 1. Bispevika 7, Oslo. Result of the correlation between the average curve from the two samples and diverse Northern European site and master chronologies. The source of the chronologies is given. The grey tone highlights the high t -values.

To estimate the felling date of the trees used in the boat a sapwood statistic for Norway is used. Oaks here have, on average, 15 (-8 +6) sapwood years (Christensen & Havemann 1998). For measuring and for the analysis and the calculation of the t -value (" t -test"), "DENDRO" (Tyers, 1997) and "CROS" (Baillie & Pilcher, 1973) are used. In the analysis master and site chronologies for Northern Europe are employed.

Literature

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Catalogue

Filename	sample title and number	rings	start yr.	end yr.	pith	sapwood	bark?	Conversion	extra end	Ave. ring width mm	Interpretation / felling
Z173001a	Bispevika 7 ship Oslo B3B7 2014096 03010138 x108 hudbord QUSP	147	AD1401	AD1547	G	7	N	R	S1	1,41	AD1548-61
Z173002a	Bispevika 7 ship Oslo B3B7 2014096 03010138 x131 hudbord QUSP	133	AD1354	AD1486	G	0	N	T	H1	1,40	after AD1494
Z173M001	Bispevika 7 ship Oslo B3B7 03010138 2 timbers QUSP	194	AD1354	AD1547						1,40	

Conversion: R = radial split plank, T = tangential plank, W = whole timber, S = squared whole timber, H = half timber, Q = quarter timber, O = other conversion.
Pith: C = centre, V = less than 5 rings, F = 5 – 10 rings, G = greater than 10 rings.

Aoife Daly, Ph.D. 21st June 2016

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in publication bibliography/literature lists:	Daly, Aoife, 2016. Dendrochronological analysis of timbers from the ship Bispevika 7, Oslo. <i>dendro.dk report 2016:37</i> , Copenhagen.
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